

(This document has two sections: A and B)

Section A

Seed selection in the data-graph.

In the paper, we chose seed-vertices such that (i) the resulting Steiner-tree is a connected-component, (ii) majority of seed-vertices are not directly connected in which case shortest-path computation could converge faster (to avoid a potential favorable scenario). Here, we discuss two alternative seed selection approaches that we have explored:

1. Uniform random selection of seed-vertices from the largest connected-component. This does not always respect requirement (ii) above, especially for smaller graphs e.g., CiteSeer, MiCo.
2. Use weighted-shortest-path information between vertex pairs (within the largest connected-component) to select eccentric vertices as seeds, i.e., selected seed-vertices are guaranteed to be far away from each other. Similar to the BFS-based approach presented in the paper, this approach respects requirements (ii) above, however, is more time consuming to generate the seed-sets. (In the paper, we evaluated our solution using 30 different instances.)

Section B

Example Steiner-trees in different graphs identified by our distributed solution.

In the figures below, seed-vertices (S) have red fill. The “Steiner vertices” have blue fill. These results suggest our seed selection approach meet one of our goals: majority of the seed-vertices are not always directly connected. Also, we do not observe any bias in these results.

Fig. B.1. Friendster graph: $|S|=10$.

Fig. B.2. Friendster graph: $|S|=100$.

Fig. B.3. Friendster graph: $|S|=1000$.

Fig. B.4. MiCo graph: $|S|=10$.

Fig. B.5. MiCo graph: $|S|=100$.

Fig. B.6. MiCo graph: $|S|=1000$.

Fig. B.7. CiteSeer graph: $|S|=10$.

Fig. B.8. CiteSeer graph: $|S|=100$.

Fig. B.9. CiteSeer graph: $|S|=1000$. The CiteSeer graph has only 3.3K vertices and the largest connected component has just over 2K vertices. When $|S| = 1000$, $1/3$ of the graph vertices are source vertices.